

EFFECTS OF ATTAPULGITE NANORODS ON MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PERFORMANCES OF SILICON-CONTAINING POLYARYLACETYLENE

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ABSTRACT

Rod-like attapulgite silicate particles (ATT) were introduced into a silicon-containing polyarylacetylene resin (PSA) in solution. ATT/PSA nanocomposites were prepared by sonication, evaporation and thermal polymerization. The effect of ATT nanorods on the curing reaction of PSA was studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) in situ monitoring. The ATT/PSA dispersions and particle networks were characterized by rheological and microscopic measurements. The addition of ATT nanorods decreased the conversion of the external acetylenic groups in PSA. However, the ATT nanorods played a pseudo-catalytic role when the large amount of ATT was added. The percolated ATT particle networks were constructed in PSA when 10 wt% ATT nanorods were added in the mixture. The flexural property of the cured PSA decreased and then increased with the addition of ATT nanorods. The addition of 10% mass fractions of ATT nanorods in PSA matrix increased the flexural strength and modulus of the nanocomposite to 52 MPa and 49.9 GPa, respectively. The thermal stability of the cured ATT/PSA nanocomposites were determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in N₂. The temperature at 5% mass loss (Td₅) and the residual at 800 °C (Y_c at 800 °C) of the nanocomposites reached 604 °C and 92.7%, respectively, when the loading of ATT nanorods was 5% mass fractions. The nanoparticle networks reduced the cyclotrimerization in PSA resulting in more linear or branched structures. The crosslink density and structure of the nanocomposites affected the flexural property and thermal stability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymers such as epoxy, polyimide, polybenzimidazole, polybenzothiazole and polybenzooxazole have been explored for decades due to their special thermal stability and mechanical properties. Epoxy is moldable at a relatively low temperature but regrettably with a challenging thermal stability property. Polyimides have a significantly high heat-resistance with a heat distortion temperature of 360 °C, but it usually processes at higher temperature. Polybenzimidazole, polybenzothiazole and polybenzooxazole with a higher heat resistance than the polyimides are not moldable and are flammable. Silicon-containing polymers are newly explored materials, which are light, highly heat-resistant, nonflammable, and moldable [1-3]. They could be potentially applied in information, electronics, and aerospace fields due to their particular thermal, mechanical, conducting and optical characteristics. As a novel highly heat-resistant silicon-containing polymer, silicon-containing polyarylacetylene resin (PSA) was prepared by dehydrogenative reaction and condensation reaction. The silicon atoms were introduced and distributed along with the polyarylethynylene backbone to form hybrids. It is soluble in solvent, fusible, and moldable at 100-150 °C, and shows highly heat- and burning-resistant properties [5, 6]. However, as a thermosetting resin, the silicon-containing polyarylacetylene exhibits brittle disadvantage after cured by cyclotrimerization, coupling reaction and so on. The fiber-reinforced PSA shows sufficient mechanical strength even at 400 °C under air. The composites can also transfer to glassy material (C-SiC) when heated at above 1000 °C under argon [7, 8]. Moreover, polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (POSS) were also successfully combined into PSA and exhibited excellent thermal properties [9]. The introduction of inorganic nanoparticles with

spherical, fibrous and platelike shape to organic polymers can form hybrid organic-inorganic nanocomposites. The nanocomposites display enhancement in thermal, mechanical and functional properties, especially excellent strength/toughness balance. The application of micro-particles (spherical and fibrous) exhibits the highest effect on brittle matrix systems. Norman and Robertson [10] investigated the nature of the toughening of glassy polymers using aligned assemblages of spherical bare glass particles with mean particle diameter of 20 μm . The localized inelastic matrix deformation, particle-matrix debonding, and crack pinning and bowing (or crack tip deformation) are the primary toughening mechanisms.

Natural fibrous or rod-like silicate particles, such as attapulgite (ATT) are inexpensive and easily exfoliated due to relatively weak inter-rod interactions [11]. A mineral ATT has been used in polymer nanocomposites as reinforcement to improve thermal/mechanical stability. Nanorod ATT not only effectively increased the thermal and mechanical properties of epoxy [12, 13], polyimides [14-16], cyanate ester [17], and bismaleimides [18], but also simultaneously enhanced the toughness of the polymers. The incorporation of nanorod ATT in hydrogels greatly enhanced the compressive strength and toughness of the composites depending on clay content, especially the forming of three dimensional (3D) networks which had overcome the disadvantages of phase separation and aggregation [19].

In this work, the inexpensive pristine ATT nanorods were dispersed in PSA solution to produce the ATT/PSA nanocomposites. The construction of three dimensional (3D) networks of ATT/PSA nanocomposites was studied, and the effect of ATT nanoparticles on the mechanical and thermal properties of PSA was also explored. Moreover, it is significant to pay attention to the catalytic effect of ATT nanorod on the curing reaction of PSA.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Silicon-containing polyarylacetylene resin was synthesized by Grignard process described in the reference [6] (see Scheme 1, $M_n=2270$ and $PD=1.97$ by SEC). Attapulgite (ATT) was received from Nanda Zhijin Science & Technology Group Co., Ltd (China). Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd., and refluxed with sodium/benzophenoneketyl, and then distilled under nitrogen atmosphere before used in PSA synthesis.

Scheme 1 Structure of PSA

2.2 Preparation of ATT/PSA

To a three-necked round-bottom flask, various amount of ATT nanorods (3g, 5g, 7g, 10g, and 15g) and 100 mL deionized water were added. The suspension was mechanically stirred under high shearing rate with ultrasonication to remove impurities such as carbonates and other hydrosoluble impurities. After centrifugation, the supernatant water was removed. Fresh deionized water was added into the sedimentation and the centrifuge tube was vibrated vigorously to form a homogenous suspension again. Those previous procedures were repeated for 3 times to get purified ATT. The final sedimentation was dried at 160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum for 24 h. The dried ATT nanorods was ground and dispersed in 500 mL purified THF. The relevant PSA (97g, 95g, 93g, 90g, and 85g) was added to the ATT/THF suspension with vigorous stirring under ultrasonication for 1 h to form a homogenous ATT/PSA/THF suspension. To remove THF, the suspension was then stirred at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum with a high-shear rate of 500 rpm for 1 h. The resulting ATT/PSA mixture was further stirred at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum for 2 h and then poured into a wild-mouth bottle which was frozen in fridge to form homogenous ATT/PSA mixtures. The ATT/PSA nanocomposites were prepared after cured at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

/2 h, 170 °C/2 h, 210 °C/2 h, and 250 °C/4 h. The nanocomposites with various mass fraction of ATT (3%, 5%, 7%, 10% and 15%) in PSA were coded as PSA-3ATT, PSA-5ATT, PSA-7ATT, PSA-10ATT, and PSA-15ATT, respectively. A free-ATT PSA was named as PSA-0ATT.

2.3 Characterization

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, TA Q2000) was used to study the thermal characteristics of ATT/PSA samples during curing. The samples were heated at the rate of 10 °C/min from 40 °C to 400 °C under a nitrogen flow of 40 mL/min. The curing reaction heat of samples was calculated by integrating the exothermal peak area. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Mettler-Toledo TGA/DSC1) were used to monitor the thermal stability of the cured samples. The samples were heated from 30 °C to 900 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen purge with a flow of 60 mL/min.

Fourier transform infrared (Nicolet 5700 FTIR) spectroscopy was used to study the curing process of samples in situ monitoring. The samples were grounded with KBr into powders and pressed to form a round pellet. The pellet was put into a hot cell (Thermo's HT-32) which was programmatically temperature controlled. The samples were cured in the hot cell under air atmosphere. The samples were heated at the rate of 5 °C/min from 30 °C to 250 °C and then kept at constant temperature of 250 °C for 4 h. The FTIR data was collected per minute, each spectrum with 8 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Rheological measurements of ATT/PSA mixtures were performed on a rheometer (ThermoHakke, RS600) at 120°C, using a 30 mm diameter plate-plate fixture. Samples were placed on the plate and stabilized at 120°C for 10 min before tests. An oscillation frequency-controlled strain sweep and a strain-controlled oscillation frequency sweep were conducted. The strain sweep was performed in a stress range of 0.01-100% under the oscillation frequency of 1 Hz. The oscillation frequency sweeps were performed in a frequency range of 0.1-100 Hz with an applied strain of 0.5% when the sample was a linear viscoelastic material.

Flexural properties of the ATT/PSA nanocomposites were measured by a universal testing machine (Changchun Research Institute for mechanical Science Co., Ltd.). Three-point bend fixture was used and all tests were carried out at room temperature. The loading of speed is 1 mm/min. The number of testing specimen was not less than six for each test, following Chinese National Standards (GB/T2570-1995). The size of the samples were 80 mm×15 mm×4 mm. Flexural strength, σ_f was calculated from equation (1):

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3P \cdot L}{2b \cdot h^2} \quad (1)$$

Where P is the applied force (N) at the breaking point, L is the span (mm) between two fulcrums, b is the sample width and h is the sample depth. Flexural modulus, E_f was calculated using equation (2):

$$E_f = \frac{\Delta F \cdot L^3}{4b \cdot h^3} \quad (2)$$

Where ΔF is the slope in the linear region of the force-deformation curve.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi S-4800) was used to observe the dispersion of ATT particles in PSA matrix. The fractural surface of the broken samples was coated by gold using spraying process before viewing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Curing process

DSC is a one of approaches to understand the thermal curing process of PSA during elevating temperature. Figure 1 shows the curing reaction of the ATT/PSA nanocomposites with different loadings of ATT, and the DSC data are listed in Table 1. The results denote that the thermal self-polymerization of PSA and ATT/PSA possess an exothermal process, and the near peak temperatures of PSA and ATT/PSA are shown during curing. The single exothermal peak indicates that the curing reactions of acetylenic groups in PSA occur one after the other in the range of 200 °C to 300 °C. The cure enthalpy (ΔH) of PSA decreases with addition of ATT nanorods, and declines from 628.4J/g to

524.9 J/g with increasing loads of ATT nanorods. The cure enthalpy of the ATT/PSA decreases by nearly 16.6% when the loading mass fraction of ATT nanorods is 15%. A decrease in T_p of ATT/cyanate ester (CE) as well as cure enthalpy ΔH with increasing nanorod mass fraction presented in accordance with DSC curves of ATT/CE nanocomposites [17]. Firstly, the reactive groups in PSA decrease with addition of ATT nanorods. The ratio of curing reaction among the terminal acetylenic groups in ATT/PSA was dropped. Secondly, it implies that the inorganic ATT nanorods do not take part in the curing reaction of PSA.

Figure1: DSC curves of different ATT/PSA nanocomposites

ATT Mass Fractions in ATT/PSA/%	Cure peak temperature, T_p /°C	Cure enthalpy, ΔH /J·g ⁻¹
0	243.3	628.4
3	246.6	585.8
5	249.7	544.0
10	245.8	525.5
15	243.4	524.9

Table 1: DSC results of different ATT/PSA Nanocomposites

In situ FTIR technology has been used to monitor the conversion of the functional groups in polymer at different reaction temperatures. FTIR in situ monitoring was used to study the conversion of the ethynylene groups in PSA with elevating temperature. The result showed that the content of ethynylene groups increased contrarily. In addition to cyclotrimerization of terminal acetylenic groups, the coupling reaction of the terminal acetylenic groups occurred simultaneously [20]. The effect of ATT nanorods on the curing reaction of PSA was also carefully explored by FT-IR in situ monitoring. The absorption peak at 3290 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching vibration of C-H in terminal acetylenic groups, and changes during curing. The absorption peak at 1254 cm⁻¹ which is ascribed to the Si-C stretching vibration is basically constant during curing, and could be chosen as the internal standard in order to eliminate the error caused by the change of the sample thickness during the heating and curing. The conversion of the terminal acetylenic groups was calculated by the equation (3), which was carried out in terms of the reference [20, 21].

$$\alpha = \frac{(C_0 - C)}{C_0} = \frac{\frac{A_1^0}{A_2^0} - \frac{A_1}{A_2}}{\frac{A_1^0}{A_2^0}} \quad (3)$$

Where α is the conversion ratio, C_0 and C are taken as the initial concentration and the concentration at time t of terminal acetylenic groups, respectively. A_1^0 and A_1 are the initial absorbance and the absorbance at time t of terminal acetylenic groups at 3290cm⁻¹ and could be confirmed as the

integrated intensity of the band. A_2^0 and A_2 are the initial absorbance and the absorbance at time t of Si-CH₃ at 1254cm⁻¹, and could also be confirmed as the integrated intensity of the band.

As shown in Figure 2, the conversion ratio of terminal acetylenic groups of PSA increased rapidly to 23% in the range of 50 °C-100 °C, and enhanced gradually before 175 °C, and then augmented steeply to 71% after 175 °C. The conversion ratio of terminal acetylenic groups of ATT/PSA nanocomposites increased gradually before 175 °C, and was less than that of PSA, and then ascended steeply after 175 °C. The conversion ratio of the nanocomposites increases a few with increasing mass fraction of ATT in PSA. The results indicate that the curing reaction of terminal acetylenic groups in the nanocomposites was retarded by the addition of ATT nanorods. With increase mass fraction of ATT in PSA, the agglomerates of ATT nanorods occur and result in decreasing the block of ATT to the curing reaction.

Figure2: The changes of the conversion ratios of terminal acetylenic groups in PSA and ATT/PSA with temperature

Figure 3 shows the isothermal conversion ratios of PSA and ATT/PSA nanocomposites with time at 250 °C. The conversion ratios of the terminal acetylenic groups in PSA and PSA with 5% mass fraction of ATT change a few with prolonging the time at 250 °C. The conversion ratio of PSA retains about 80% in 4 h. The conversion ratio of PSA-5ATT changes a few, and is lower than that of PSA. It results from the homogeneous dispersion of the ATT nanorods in PSA. The well-dispersed ATT nanorods obstruct the curing reaction of the acetylenic groups. The less the possibility of the reaction is, the lower the conversion ratio of PSA-5ATT achieves. The conversion ratios of PSA-10ATT and PSA-15ATT are lower than that of PSA because of the blocking of ATT nanorods. However, the conversion ratios of the nanocomposites start to increase when the isothermal time is more than 180 min and 110 min, respectively. And the conversion ratios of the nanocomposites could increase to more than 90%. The results demonstrate that the ATT nanorods begin to agglomerate to form the free volume with increasing ATT loadings. It affords the confined space to the terminal chains with the end reactive groups to react each other. On the other hand, the activation ability of the terminal chains could increase with standing heat. The impact of free volume induced by a large amount of ATT loadings on segmental motion of the matrix is probably more important controlling factor to toughen the ATT/polyimide nanocomposites [14]. Exfoliated sodium-montmorillonite (Na⁺-MMT, a layered silicate) in polymer matrix played a pseudo-catalytic role and accelerated the cross-linking kinetics by hastening the formation of chemical connection between the polymer monomers [22]. Presumably, the large amount of rod-like ATT could play a pseudo-catalytic role, the reaction kinetics and the network of the organic components altered and the conversion ratio increased.

Figure 3: The changes of the conversion ratios of the reactive groups in PSA and ATT/PSA with time at 250 °C

3.2 Rheological behavior

Winter and Chambon [23] found that the storage and loss moduli of crosslinking polymers are congruent: $G'(\omega) \approx G''(\omega)$ at the gel point, which means that the $\tan\delta$ at this point is independent of the frequency. This makes it possible to measure exactly the instant of gelation of a crosslinking polymer without stopping the crosslinking reaction. Figure 4 shows the effects of nanorods on G' and G'' of the neat PSA and the ATT/PSA mixtures at 120 °C. The results reflect that the ATT nanorods could construct the inorganic particle networks with increasing ATT contents. It is a percolation threshold up to 10% mass fraction of ATT in the mixtures, the $\tan\delta$ is independent of frequency, which is close to the value of 9.0 wt% in ATT/CE systems [17].

Figure 4: Dynamic rheological curves for PSA resins with different ATT loadings under dynamic frequency with strain of 0.5%: loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) versus frequency (ω)

3.3 Mechanical property

The flexural strength σ_f and modulus E_f of the cured PSA and ATT/PSA nanocomposites are illustrated as histogram in Figure 5, and error bars are also marked. The results show that the flexural property of PSA firstly drops with addition of ATT nanorods, and then ascends with increase of ATT loadings. However, the flexural property of ATT/PSA nanocomposite decreases again when 15 wt% of ATT nanorods are added in PSA. In comparison with the cured PSA, the flexural strength and

modulus of the nanocomposite increased by 21% and 1.6% (52 MPa and 49.9 GPa), respectively, when 10% mass fractions of ATT nanorods were added in PSA resin. The addition of 3 wt% ATT nanorods caused the distinct decrease of the flexural property of the cured PSA. The reduction arose from the decrease of the PSA crosslink density. The effect of ATT on the conversion of PSA in Figure 2 can prove the explanation as well. The particle networks gradually construct with increase of ATT loadings. The percolated particle networks were formed when the 10 wt% ATT nanorods were added in PSA. The integration and interpenetration of inorganic ATT networks and organic PSA crosslink networks result in the maximal flexural property of the nanocomposite. On the other hand, the enhancement of the conversion of acetylenic groups in PSA containing 10 wt% ATT loadings increases the crosslink density of PSA, and conduces the augment of the flexural property. The phenomenon is consistent with early reports. In the presence of bare ATT nanorods, the modulus, strength, and toughness of double network hydrogels (DN gels) are significantly improved in comparison to those of the conventional DN gels [19]. The maximal mechanical properties of the ATT reinforced polymers achieved when the percolated ATT networks constructed in polymers [14, 17]. The aggregation of ATT and increase of free volume in PSA made the defects in the nanocomposite, and the σ_f value of the nanocomposite incurred loss when PSA was reinforced with addition of 15 wt% ATT nanorods. However, the rigid ATT nanorods did not affect the E_f value of the nanocomposite, and the more crosslink density of PSA-15ATT (shown in Figure 3) was only beneficial to the increase of flexural modulus of the nanocomposite.

Figure 5: Flexural strength and modulus of the cured ATT/PSA nanocomposites

The morphology of the cured PSA and ATT/PSA fractured section are shown Figure 6. The fractured surface of the cured PSA presents a smooth ribbon. It is a typical feature of the fractured section of the thermosetting polymers. The fractured surface of the nanocomposites became rough and ridgy with addition of ATT nanorods. The well-embedded ATT nanorods in PSA matrix are also visible. The homogenous dispersion of ATT nanorods in PSA can be clearly sighted since the natural ATT nanorods are easily exfoliated due to its relatively weak inter-rod interactions. The white dot and needle protuberances on the fractured surface of the nanocomposites are ascribed to the randomly oriented ATT nanorods. The most of light point or stub of nanorods are the fractured ATT. Some of ATT nanorods were pulled out from the matrix to form the needlelike tubers on the section when the applied strength was larger than the interaction between the nanorods and the PSA matrix, which indicated that interface interaction of the nanorods and PSA was weak. The confinement of organic crosslink networks results in the irregular orientation of ATT nanorods. Indeed, the pores commence to present on the section of the nanocomposites with increase of ATT loadings because of the aggregation of ATT nanorods and increase of the free volume in the matrix.

Figure 6: SEM images of the fracture surfaces of the cured ATT/PSA nanocomposites

3.4 Thermal stability

The effect of ATT nanorods on the thermal stability of PSA network can be determined from thermogravimetric experiments (see Figure 7). The temperature at 5% mass loss (T_{d5}) and char yield (Y_c) at 800°C for all samples are summarized in Table 2. As a consequence, the thermal stability of the ATT/PSA nanocomposites decreases with increase of ATT loadings in initial decomposition stage in N_2 . It is due to the loss of water that is adsorbed on the surface of the pristine ATT nanorods. The temperature at 5% mass loss and the residual at 800 °C of the nanocomposite reach 604 °C and 92.7%, respectively, when the loading of ATT nanorods is 5% mass fractions. The T_{d5} of the nanocomposites decrease when the loading of the nanorods is more than 10% mass fractions. The effect of the loading of nanorods on Y_c at 800°C of the nanocomposites is limited in comparison with the cured PSA resin. The increase of ATT loadings compensated the loss of the PSA matrix during pyrolysis. The addition of 15 wt% ATT in PSA decreased T_{d5} of the nanocomposite by 15°C. The more loading of ATT nanorods resulted in enhancement of aggregation of ATT particles and free volume in the nanocomposite, and decrease of crosslink density and the number of cyclotrimerization rings. As a result, the more linear short chains and branches of PSA could be further formed and induced the decrease of the thermal stability of nanocomposites. It implies that the increase of conversion of external alkynes in PSA (see Figure 3) originated from the coupling reaction and free radical polymerization. This reflects the addition of bare ATT nanorods affects the crosslink density and structure of the organic networks.

Figure 7: TGA curves of the cured ATT/PSA nanocomposites

ATT Mass Fractions	T _{d5%} (°C)	Y _c at 800°C (%)
0%	593.26	92.22
3%	590.24	91.56
5%	604.33	92.70
7%	597.71	91.92
10%	588.35	92.69
15%	578.36	92.96

Table 2: Thermal stability of the cured ATT/PSA nanocomposites with different loadings

4 CONCLUSION

The effects of ATT nanorods on PSA resins are very complex. We explored systematically the curing process of PSA and ATT/PSA mixtures, the construction of the particle network in the PSA matrix and influence on the flexural property and thermal stability of the nanocomposites. The addition of ATT nanorods decreased the conversion of the acetylenic groups in PSA. The ATT nanorods played a pseudo-catalytic role when the large amount of ATT was added in PSA. The rheological behavior of the ATT/PSA mixtures manifested that the percolation threshold achieved when 10 wt% ATT nanorods were added. The flexural strength and modulus of the nanocomposite achieved 52 MPa and 49.9 GPa, respectively, when 10% mass fractions of ATT nanorods were added in PSA resin. In comparison with the cured PSA, the flexural strength of the nanocomposites increased by 21%. The formation of the percolated nanorod networks in the crosslinked PSA matrix enhanced the flexural property of the PSA-10ATT nanocomposite. The homogenous dispersion of ATT nanorods in the matrix was visible in SEM images. The inorganic particle networks can not improve the thermal stability of the cured PSA. The effect of ATT nanorods on the char yield at 800 °C of the cured PSA is limited. Whereas, the incorporation of aggregation of ATT nanorods and increase of free volume in the nanocomposites conduces the decrease of T_{d5%}. The crosslink density and structure of the nanocomposites play crucial roles in improvement of the flexural property and thermal stability.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Ishikawa, T.Hatano, Y. Hasegawa, T.Horio, A. Kunai, A.Miyai, T. Ishida, T.Tsukihara, T. Yamanaka, T. Koike, J.Shioya, Polymeric organosilicon systems. 12. synthesis and anionicing-opening polymerization of 1,2,5,6-tetrasilacycloocta-3,7-diyne, *Organometallics*, **11**, 1992, pp.1604-1618.(doi: 10.1021/om00040a035)

- [2] L. Ye, W. Han, R. Zhang, J. Hu, T. Zhao, Synthesis, characterization, and properties of silylene-acetylene preceramic polymers, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **110**, 2008, pp.4064-4070.(doi: 10.1002/app.28996)
- [3] M. Chen, Q. Zhou, L. Ni, G. Wang, Synthesis, cure and pyrolysis behavior of heat-resistant boron-silicon hybrid polymer containing acetylene, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **126**, 2012, pp.1322-1327.(doi: 10.1002/app.36960)
- [5] M. Itoh, K. Inoue, K. Iwata, M. Mitsuzuka, T. Kakigano, New Highly Heat-Resistant Polymers Containing Silicon: Poly(silyleneethynylene phenyleneethynylene)s, *Macromolecules*, **30**, 1997, pp.694-701.(doi: 10.1021/ma961081f)
- [6] F. Wang, J. Zhang, J. Huang, H. Yan, F. Huang, and L. Du, Synthesis and Characterization of Poly(dimethylsilyleneethynylene phenyleneethynylene) Terminated with Phenylacetylene, *Polymer Bulletin*, **56**, 2006, pp.19-26.
- [7] C. Wang, F. Huang, Y. Jiang, Y. Zhou, and L. Du, A novel oxidation resistant SiC/B₄C/C nanocomposite derived from a carborane-containing conjugated polycarbosilane, *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, **95**, 2012, pp.71-74.(doi: 10.1111/j.1551-2916.2011.04972.x)
- [8] Y. Jiang, J. Li, F. Huang, Y. Zhou, and L. Du, Polymer-derived SiC/B₄C/C nanocomposites: Structural evolution and crystallization behavior, *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, **97**, 2014, pp.310-315 (doi: 10.1111/jace.12670).
- [9] Z. Jiang, Y. Zhou, F. Huang and L. Du, Characterization of a modified silicon-containing arylacetylene resin with POSS functionality, *Chinese Journal of Polymer Science*, **29**, 2011, pp.726-731.(doi:10.1007/s10118-011-1086-y)
- [10] D. A. Norman, R. E. Robertson, Rigid-particle toughening of glassy polymers, *Polymer*, **44**, 2003, pp.2351-2362 (doi:10.1016/S0032-3861(03)00084-3).
- [11] E. Galan, Properties and applications of palygorskite-sepiolite clays, *Clay Minerals*, **31**, 1996, pp.443-453.
- [12] Y. Sun, Y. Zhang, K. Xu, W. Xu, D. Yu, L. Zhu, H. Xie, R. Cheng, Thermal, mechanical properties, and low-temperature performance of fibrous nanoclay-reinforced epoxy asphalt composites and their concretes, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **132**, 2015, (doi:10.1002/app.41694)
- [13] X. Niu, L. Huo, C. Cai, J. Guo, and H. Zhou, Rod-like attapulgite modified by bifunctional acrylic resin as reinforcement for epoxy composites, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, **53**, 2014, pp.16359-16365.(doi: 10.1021/ie502869c)
- [14] L. An, Y. Pan, X. Shen, H. Lu, Y. Yang, Rod-like attapulgite/polyimide nanocomposites with simultaneously improved strength, toughness, thermal stability and related mechanisms, *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, **18**, 2008, pp.4928-4941(doi:10.1039/b805849k).
- [15] Y. Zhang, J. Shen, Q. Li, L. Pang, Z. Xu, K. W. K. Yeung, C. Yi, Effect of the adding of rod-like attapulgite upon the properties of polyimides produced by random copolycondensation, *Journal of Materials Science*, **48**, 2013, pp.4973-4982(doi:10.1007/s10853-013-7281-1)
- [16] Y. Zhang, J. Shen, Q. Li, Z. Xu, K. W. K. Yeung, C. Yi, Q. Zhang, Development and characterization of co-polyimide/attapulgite nanocomposites with highly enhanced thermal and mechanical properties, *Polymer Composites*, **35**, 2014, pp.86-96.(doi: 10.1002/pc.22637)
- [17] Y. Pan, Y. Xu, L. An, H. Lu, Y. Yang, W. Chen, and S. Nutt, Hybrid network structure and mechanical properties of rodlike silicate/cyanate ester nanocomposites, *Macromolecules*, **41**, 2008, pp.9245-9258(doi:10.1021/ma800819s).
- [18] L. Zhao, P. Liu, G. Liang, A. Gu, L. Yuan, Q. Guan, The origin of the curing behavior, mechanical and thermal properties of surface functionalized attapulgite/bismaleimide/diallylbisphenol composites, *Applied Surface Science*, **288**, 2014, pp.435-443.(doi:10.1016/j.apsusc.2013.10.052)
- [19] G. Gao, G. Du, Y. Cheng and J. Fu, Tough nanocomposite double network hydrogels reinforced with clay nanorods through covalent bonding and reversible chain adsorption, *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, **2**, 2014, pp.1539-1548(doi:10.1039/c3tb21554g).
- [20] Y. Shen, Q. Yuan, F. Huang, L. Du, Effect of neutral nickel catalyst on cure process of silicon-containing polyarylacetylene, *Thermochimica Acta*, **590**, 2014, pp. 66-72.(doi: 10.1016/j.tca.2014.06.002)

- [21] S.Xue, Z. Zhang, S. Ying, Reaction kinetics of polyurethane/polystyrene interpenetrating polymer networks by infra-red spectroscopy, *Polymer*, **30**, 1989, pp.1269-1274.(doi:10.1016/0032-3861(89)90047-5)
- [22] S. Pour-Esmaeil, N. T.Qazvini, H.Mahdavi, Interpenetrating polymer networks (IPN) based on gelatin/poly(ethylene glycol) dimethacrylate/clay nanocomposites: Structure-properties relationship, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, **143**, 2014, pp.1396-1403.(doi:10.1016/j.matchemphys.2013.11.052)
- [23] H. H. Winter, F. Chambon, Analysis of linear viscoelasticity of a crosslinking polymer at the gel point, *Journal of Rheology*, **30**, 1986, pp.367-382(doi:10.1122/1.549853).